

A Model for Contact Forces Distribution Estimation in Adaptive Feet

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Abstract—Most prosthetic and robotic feet are still far from reaching the functionality and versatility of the human foot. The rigid and flat design prevents the foot from adapting to different terrains. The SoftFoot is a recently presented foot prototype designed to adapt its sole to ground unevenness. The exploitation of its adaptability requires novel sensor systems to estimate the distribution of forces on the foot sole. This study proposes a model-based approach to reconstruct the contact forces distribution, using the knowledge of the foot shape as input. The foot model is formalized and analyzed with a quasi-static method in the sagittal plane with the hypothesis of elastic contact between the foot and the ground. A software implementation of the model shows its capability to reconstruct the forces acting on the sole.

Index Terms—SoftFoot, adaptability, estimation, model-based

I. INTRODUCTION

The human foot can change its mechanical properties according to the different gait phases. While it functions as a rigid lever to push the body forward, it uses softness at heel contact to dampen the impact and add stability [1]. Moreover, the foot has the adaptive capability to withstand any terrain by adjusting its structure.

Despite the efforts in the last decades, the designs of artificial feet still have to reach the functionality of their human counterpart [2]. Nowadays, different types of prosthetic feet are commercially available. Even though some devices stabilize the ankle-foot system for ground adaptation, they all adopt a flat sole, leading to poor stability, compensatory movements, and additional stress on the residual limb [4]. Consequently, navigating uneven terrain still poses a challenge for lower-limb prosthetic device users who report as a relevant limitation the inability to walk on natural surfaces [3].

A few years ago, our research group introduced the SoftFoot, an anthropomorphic foot designed to be intrinsically adaptive [5]. The robotic prototype replicates the function of the human foot's longitudinal arch, ensuring shock absorption and ground adaptability in the sagittal plane. Despite being a promising, appealing alternative to flat devices, SoftFoot still has room for improvement. It is a passive device whose adaptability relies only on the sole mechanical intelligence and has no sensor. The development into an active prosthesis could lead to an adaptability increment and user effort reduction

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Fig. 1. Simulated representation of the SoftFoot model. The foot adapts its shape to the ground profile, represented by the brown dashed line. The weight force is applied to the ankle joint, and contact forces arise to balance it.

during the push-off. Sensing the foot's interaction with the ground provides valuable feedback to stabilize the prosthesis actively.

In [6], a model for the SoftFoot was presented with an algorithm that provides forces evaluation and distribution on the foot sole based on postural information under precise hypothesis. Inspired by previous work on the soft synergies approach for hand grasping [7], in this research work, we aim at reconstructing forces distribution at the contact surface with a quasi-static grasping-like approach based on the foot sole deformation, exploiting its intrinsic adaptability to the environment. For the sake of simplicity, we restrict the analysis to a two-dimensional problem by investigating the phenomenon in the sagittal plane only (as this simplified analysis accounts for a non-negligible fragment of the whole phenomenon).

II. SOFTFOOT MODEL

A. SoftFoot Structure

The SoftFoot can be disassembled into four rigid components and an adaptive sole. The rigid structure consists of the rear arch p , frontal arch a , heel h , and metatarsus m . Two articulated subsystems, the toe, and the plantar fascia, made of small rigid links coupled with rolamite joints kept in contact by elastic ligaments, constitute the adaptive sole. As stated in [6], the sole links and their coupling can be modeled as a three-bar mechanism made of real and virtual joints. The fascia

connects the heel with the metatarsus. All the finger and fascia modules are coupled by the same tendon, which also routes through the metatarsus and the heel. The rear arch is connected to the sole through elastic coils. We hypothesize that the foot segment masses are negligible. As a result, mass-related forces internal to the foot will be neglected, and the whole user mass W is considered gathered above the ankle. The elastic contact of the foot with the ground generates contact forces positioned in correspondence with revolute joints and the foot extremities so that the actual position on the link can be easily retrieved. The SoftFoot can be modeled as two serial kinematic chains, the plantar fascia, and the toes, that form a closed structure. A high-stiffness linear spring separates the structure and describes the relative displacement between the two open chains.

B. Walking as a Grasping Problem

The quasi-static behavior of the foot-ground system during the walking phase can be seen as the hand-object system during the grasping task proposed in [7]. The equilibrium of the foot happens when the sum of all the contact f_c and internal forces/torques f_r exerted by the foot balance the joints torque τ . The *Jacobian matrix* J , composed of J_c and J_r , maps joints velocity and the contact frame velocity. Some reaction forces arise during the contact between the foot and the ground. The contact forces variation is caused by a relative displacement of the contact points in the directions nominally forbidden by the (rigid) contact constraints. This behavior is modeled by introducing (virtual) linear springs between foot and ground contact points. Based on the soft synergies approach proposed in [7], a virtual foot is introduced in the model to attract the real foot via a generalized spring. This enables the adaptability of the foot and introduces a compliant element in each joint that determines the motion of the real joint based on the joint reference position collected in the vector q_r .

C. Fundamental Grasp Equation

The foot-ground system and its soft interaction can be described with a set of equations defining the foot statics and kinematics, the soft contact with the ground, and the force equilibrium. The quasi-static form of the system is obtained by approximating the equilibrium equations to a first-order Taylor series and multiplying both terms in the congruences for an infinitesimal amount of time. Grouping them, we obtain the equivalent of the Fundamental Grasp Equation (FGE) defined in [7]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -J_c & 0 & 0 & 0 & I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -J_r & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & I & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -Q & I & 0 & -J_c^T & 0 & -J_r^T H & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I & -I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & I & -K_c & 0 & 0 & 0 & K_c & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & I & -K_r & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ K_q & 0 & I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -K_q & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta q \\ \delta \tau \\ \delta \tau_c \\ \delta F_c \\ \delta P_c \\ \delta F_r \\ \delta P_r \\ \delta q_r \\ \delta P_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where H relates the points of the two different serial chains to the four internal forces, $Q = \frac{\delta(J^T f_c)}{\delta q}$, K_c is the matrix collecting the virtual springs at the contact point stiffness values,

and the joint stiffness matrix K_q relates the difference between the reference joint variables and the real joints to the joint torques. Eq. 1 can be written in the compact form $\Phi * \delta \psi = 0$. The matrix is evaluated in the current equilibrium point, and the variables vector $\delta \psi$ can be divided into dependent $\delta \psi_d$ and independent variables $\delta \psi_i$. The linearized system can then be solved as $\delta \psi_d = -\Phi_d^{-1} \Phi_i \delta \psi_i$.

III. RESULTS

The described model was implemented in Matlab. We considered as independent variables the contact point of the soil and the joints reference position. The infinitesimal increment results by diving, for a sufficiently high number, the difference between the independent variables initial and desired final value. At each simulation step, the independent variables are increased moving towards the final configuration, and the new equilibrium is obtained by solving the FGE. The model was tested with different terrain conformation of different heights and shapes. Fig. 1 shows the result of a simulation. The foot sole adaptiveness is well represented, and the sum of the elastic forces at the sole balances the applied weight force.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The presented SoftFoot analytical model describes the foot-ground system and has been implemented in Matlab. However, its accuracy still has to be tested. Experimental parameters identification phase must be performed to tune the parameters. Then, the model accuracy will be tested through force-foot deformation validation experiments, using the measured joints position and the joints reference as independent variables. The obtained model will be the starting point for developing an active version of the SoftFoot, as a feedback source to improve the stabilization and simulate different actuation designs.

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